

Auditory, Intellectually, Repetition (AIR) Defense Model to improve critical thinking of grade V elementary school students in IPAS subjects.

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Abstract Education is an important factor in the progress of a nation and is the main means to prepare the generation to face the challenges of the 21st century. One of the skills that is urgently needed is the ability to think critically, which is part of the profile of Pancasila students in the independent curriculum. However, the results of international surveys such as TIMSS and PISA show that the critical thinking skills of Indonesian students are still relatively low. Therefore, a learning model is needed that is able to improve these skills, especially for science subjects that integrate science and social studies. A number of previous studies have confirmed that constructivism-based learning models, such as AIR (Auditory, Intellectually, Repetition), are effective in encouraging critical thinking skills. This model emphasizes listening, reasoning, and repetition activities so that students are more active, reflective, and able to develop solutions based on in-depth analysis. Other literature also shows that the application of AIR can improve learning outcomes while building students' analytical and evaluative skills. The research method used in this article is a literature review by examining various studies related to the application of the AIR model in science learning in elementary schools. The main findings are that the application of AIR in the learning of science in grade V elementary school is able: 1. Encouraging students to actively discuss and express opinions through the auditory stage, 2. Practicing analysis, problem-solving, and critical reflection skills through the intellectually stage, 3. Strengthening understanding through repetition in the form of practice questions, material review, and evaluation at the repetition stage. In addition, the AIR model has proven to be relevant to the demands of 21st century skills, as it integrates aspects of communication, collaboration, and critical thinking. This article emphasizes that AIR can be an effective alternative learning model to improve the quality of IPAS learning while building a critical, rational, and reflective Pancasila student profile.

Keywords: Auditory, Critical Thinking, Education, Ipas, Intellectually, Repetition.

Introduction

Education is where the transformation needed can be achieved and not just a hypothesis about what is desired (Dewey, 2019). A very important factor in the progress of a country is education. Therefore, every country must be able to keep up with the changes that occur in line with the rapid development of security in the world of global education so as not to experience inequality (Noorhapizah et al., 2022). In this country, there are still a lot of children who still have low-level thinking. This is evidenced by the results of the TIMSS (Trend in international mathematic and science study) and PISA (The programme for international student assessment) survey in 2011 which placed Indonesia in the bottom 10

(Rahayuni, 2016) and the results of a PISA and OECD study in 2018 which placed Indonesia in the bottom 7 among 72 other countries (Arif et al., 2020). The survey conducted by PISA emphasizes the 21st century skills that have been recommended by the Ministry of Education and Culture's Research and Development Agency in 2013 known as the 6c (critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity, citizenship, character) which is expected to be a bridge for the nation to keep up with the demands of the global world (Asmuni et al., 2023). One of the skills needed in the development of 21st century skills is critical thinking skills (Rahardhian, 2022). Critical thinking is a person's objective ability to analyze problems based on the evidence and information available to decide (Ulfah & Sutrisno, 2025).

Critical thinking is also one of the components of the Pancasila student profile in the independent curriculum that must be realized (Noorhapizah, 2022). People with critical thinking and non-critical thinking skills are as follows: People who have critical thinking are able to analyse their weaknesses so that they can easily identify the limitations of their abilities. Meanwhile, when they have to make decisions or give judgments, it is not because they follow their group/faction, but all decisions are based on authentic and rational evidence. Meanwhile, those who do not have critical thinking skills see problems as something complex and become conflicts in the future (Maro, 2016). One of the subjects that is a new breakthrough in the implementation of the independent curriculum is the science subject which is an integrated subject that combines science and social studies subjects. IPAS is an integrated subject that guides students to develop critical and rational thinking capacity (Ratna Yulias Rahmawati, Aprilia Putri Wening, 2020). Critical thinking skills can be trained with various disciplines, one of which is the science subject which has the same goal, which is to develop critical thinking skills. In carrying out a learning process, teachers must find and choose what learning model or method is appropriate and in accordance with the conditions, materials and needs of students. The chosen model is expected to make it easier for students to grasp the material (Sutrisno, 2019).

One of the learning models that is in line with the needs of skills in the 21st century and in accordance with the goals of science subjects is to improve students' critical thinking skills, namely the AIR (Auditory, intellectually, repetition) learning model. This AIR learning model is a model that refers to the theory of constructivism where learning is student-centered (Rahayuni, 2016). This AIR learning model was chosen and considered effective in improving critical thinking skills because in the AIR learning model there is an intellectually stage, namely learning with the activity of analyzing concepts, problem solving, and critical reflection. In the AIR learning model, a learning is considered effective if it pays attention to 3 things, namely Auditory, intellectually, and repetition. Auditory is learning by listening, speaking, group discussions, presentations, and expressing opinions. Intellectually means learning by exercising students' thinking skills through reasoning exercises, analyzing concepts, solving problems, constructing and applying. Repetition is a repetition in learning so that the understanding obtained is deeper and broader, such as students are trained through working on problems, reviewing materials, daily tests, assigning assignments or quizzes (Chyta et al., 2019).

Critical thinking is critical thinking. Criticizing something means evaluating it according to a certain standard. So you can think critically about anything that makes sense to be evaluated according to standards. Among the most important things that you can criticize is reasoning, thinking that plays a role when we form opinions, make judgments, make decisions, develop plans, draw conclusions, offer hypotheses, and the like. So our goal of critical thinking is the evaluation of reasoning (Wira Suciono, 2021). Critical thinking is a

mental discipline activity for reflective thinking, and it makes sense to evaluate the arguments in decisions over what has been done. Unlike other intelligences, critical thinking can be enhanced and developed and is age-independent (Çimer et al., 2013). Cognitive skills are what experts include as the core of critical thinking: interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inferences, explanations, and self-regulation (P. A. Facione, 2015)

Basically, critical thinking is considered an appropriate statement judgment. Because there are different types of statements, variety, relationships between statements from their foundations, as well as different stages in the assessment process, we can expect that there will be different ways to make mistakes when someone tries to think critically (Ennis, 1962). Fundamental to critical thinking is the ability to judge the quality of reasoning. Assessing critical thinking involves consistently decoding and examining thoughts based on universal standards of intellectual quality.(Ralston & Bays, 2013). Critical thinking skills, like any other skill, are the ability to engage in an activity, process, or procedure. In general, having skills includes the ability to do the right thing. Being skilled at critical thinking involves knowledge, perhaps implicitly or without the ability to articulate this knowledge, either a set of procedures or when to apply it (Sternberg et al., 2006).

Problem Statement

The main problem in this study is how the application of the AIR (*Auditory, Intellectually, Repetition*) learning model can improve the critical thinking skills of grade V elementary school students in science subjects. The formulation of this problem departs from the low results of international surveys (TIMSS and PISA) which show that the critical thinking skills of Indonesian students are still weak. Therefore, this study seeks to answer the question: To what extent is the AIR learning model able to encourage students to be active, discuss, analyze problems, and strengthen understanding through repetition so that critical thinking skills can develop optimally in learning science.

Methods/literatur Riview

- a) IPAS is a scientific study that discusses living things and their interactions with the environment and the universe. For example, humans are a form of combination of natural science (IPA) and social science (IPS) (Meylovvia & Julianto, 2014). In facing something that is considered a challenge in implementing the independent curriculum in the classroom in science subjects, the action taken is to invite students to be more responsible and hold commitment. Students are encouraged to identify problems, solve problems, and present solutions to problems through products that students produce in learning project activities (I Gusti Ngurah et al., 2022).
- b) AIR learning model (*Auditory, Intellectually, Repetition*). The combination of this learning model is *Auditory* (learning by listening) i.e. through class presentations, students answer and ask questions, *Intellectually* (learning by thinking) is students discussing with friends in working on practice problems and group discussions, while *Repetition* namely by providing repetition in the form of practice questions, homework, and evaluation tests (Sakti & Hikayati, 2017).
- c) Critical thinking is a liberating education and a powerful resource in one's personal and civic life. Although it is not synonymous with thinking well, critical thinking is a pervasive human phenomenon and can improve itself. The ideal critical thinking is high curiosity, insightful, believes in common sense, open-minded, flexible, fair in evaluating, honest in dealing with personal biases, wise in making judgments, willing

to reconsider, clear in responding to issues, orderly in complex matters, diligent in seeking relevant information, rational in choosing criteria, focused in investigation, and persistent in seeking results as specific as the subject and conditions of the investigation (P. a. Facione, 2011).

Discussion

In the AIR learning model, the main stages can be applied, namely *Auditory* (Group discussion, Presentation, Listening), *Intellectually* (Concept analysis, problem solving, Critical reflection), *Repetition* (Practice questions, Review again, quiz). This AIR learning model is a model that refers to the theory of constructivism where this application can make social studies learning more student-centered and can encourage students to be active and able to think critically.

Example of AIR model steps in learning social studies.

AIR Stages	Teacher & Student Activities	Trained Critical Thinking Activities
Auditory	The teacher conveys learning objectives and problems orally. Students listen, discuss, and express opinions.	Students can Identify Problems, understand context, craft initial arguments.
Intellectually	The teacher organizes students to analyze the problem. Students collect data, analyze information and design solutions.	Students can analyze concepts, problem-solving, critical reflection, evaluate arguments.
Repetition	Students compile reports/presentations, repeat practice questions, review materials, and revise results. The teacher gives feedback.	Students can strengthen understanding, reframe arguments, repeat evaluations, improve solutions.

Examples of AIR model steps in English language learning (Listening).

AIR Stages	Teacher & student activities	Trained critical thinking activities
Auditory	The teacher conveys the learning objectives and provides stimulus in the form of reading texts, audio, or English conversations. Whereas students listen, respond to open-ended questions, and identify key ideas.	Students can identify key ideas, understand context, craft initial arguments, and listen to friends' opinions.

Intellectually	The teacher organizes students to analyze the text or dialogue. Meanwhile, students ask critical questions, conduct mini debates, role plays, or analyze vocabulary and sentence structure.	Students can analyze texts, evaluate arguments, critically reflect, test logic, and can develop alternative solutions.
Repetition	Students repeat the critical thinking process through summary writing exercises, written opinions, presentations, or repetitive conversations. Meanwhile, the teacher gives feedback for improvement.	Students can strengthen understanding, reframe arguments, refine the structure of ideas, and can conduct repetitive evaluations.

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